

Characterization of Bacterial Isolates and Antibiotic Resistance in Endotracheal Secretions: A Clinical Study

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Abstract:

Objective: This study aims to characterize bacterial isolates and evaluate antibiotic resistance patterns in endotracheal secretions of mechanically ventilated patients in intensive care units (ICUs).

Methods: A total of 120 endotracheal aspirate samples were collected from ICU patients at MGM Medical College between June 2018 and May 2019. Bacterial identification was performed using Gram staining, culture on selective media, and biochemical tests. Antibiotic susceptibility was assessed using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method according to Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software version 20.

Results: Bacterial growth was detected in 86 samples (71.67%), with 52 samples (43.33%) showing monomicrobial growth and 34 samples (28.33%) exhibiting polymicrobial growth. The predominant isolates were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (35.83%), *Acinetobacter baumannii* (24.16%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (23.33%). High resistance rates were observed, particularly among *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. Extended Spectrum β -Lactamases (ESBL) were present in 54.54% of *Escherichia coli* and 18.60% of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) constituted 87.50% of the *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates.

Conclusion: The study highlights a significant prevalence of multi-drug-resistant organisms, including ESBL-producing strains and MRSA, in endotracheal secretions from ICU patients. These findings underscore the necessity for targeted antimicrobial therapy and robust infection control measures to address the high levels of resistance and improve patient outcomes in critical care settings.

Keywords: Hospital-acquired infections, intensive care unit, endotracheal secretions, bacterial resistance, antibiotic susceptibility, ESBL-producing bacteria, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*.

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Introduction

Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), or nosocomial infections, present significant challenges in healthcare, especially in intensive care units (ICUs). These infections are associated with increased morbidity, mortality, and extended hospital stays. In developed nations, HAIs affect approximately 15% of patients in general wards and over 50% in ICUs [1]. However, in developing countries, the true burden of HAIs is often underestimated due to complex diagnostic and surveillance processes. Common HAIs include surgical site infections, urinary tract infections, and

lower respiratory tract infections, with the latter being particularly prevalent in ICU settings [2]. The World Health Organization (WHO) has highlighted the high prevalence of HAIs in ICU patients, which is often exacerbated by underlying conditions. Invasive procedures, such as the use of catheters and mechanical ventilation, significantly contribute to the incidence of these infections. Among these, catheter-associated urinary tract infections and ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) pose the greatest risks to patient safety [3]. VAP, a severe infection affecting patients on

mechanical ventilation, is primarily caused by the colonization of the respiratory tract by pathogenic bacteria. This risk is heightened by the insertion of endotracheal tubes, which can impair the clearance of bacteria and lead to the accumulation of secretions [4]. Endotracheal aspirate cultures, a less invasive diagnostic method compared to bronchoscopy, are commonly used for early detection of the pathogens responsible for these infections. The accurate identification of these pathogens is crucial for the selection of appropriate empirical therapies, particularly given the rising prevalence of antibiotic-resistant organisms in ICU settings [5].

In mechanically ventilated patients, the risk of pneumonia is significantly increased, with rates up to 21 times higher than in non-intubated patients. This elevated risk is often due to infections caused by Gram-negative bacilli, which thrive in the lower respiratory tract under these conditions [6]. The extensive use of antibiotics in ICUs further complicates the situation by promoting the emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains, such as those producing β -lactamase enzymes. Studies have identified a range of pathogens responsible for these infections, including Staphylococci, Acinetobacter, Pseudomonas species, Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, and Staphylococcus aureus, with a significant proportion of cases being polymicrobial [7].

This study aims to characterize the bacterial isolates and antibiotic resistance patterns found in endotracheal secretions of mechanically ventilated ICU patients. By identifying the predominant pathogens early through endotracheal secretion cultures, this research seeks to inform the selection of empirical therapies and improve patient outcomes [8]. The findings will provide valuable insights into the local microbial flora and resistance patterns, aiding in the development of targeted treatment protocols and infection control strategies.

Methods

Study Setting and Approval: This prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology at MGM Medical College from June 2018 to May 2019. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional ethical committee before the commencement of the study.

Sample Collection: A total of 120 endotracheal aspirate samples were collected from patients admitted to various intensive care units (ICUs).

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients who were on mechanical ventilators for more than 48 hours were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who were on mechanical ventilators for less than 48 hours.
- Repeat samples from patients already enrolled in the study.

Microbiological Processing: All endotracheal secretion samples were processed immediately upon receipt in the microbiology laboratory.

Gram Stain Procedure

1. A thin smear was prepared on a clean glass slide and air-dried.
2. The smear was heat-fixed by passing the slide over a flame 2-3 times.
3. The slide was flooded with crystal violet solution for 1 minute, then washed with water.
4. Gram's iodine was applied for 1 minute, followed by washing.
5. The slide was decolorized with alcohol until no more violet color washed off, then washed with water.
6. Safranin was used as a counterstain for 1 minute, followed by washing.
7. The slide was air-dried and examined under a 100X oil immersion objective.
8. Interpretation: Gram-positive bacteria appeared dark purple, while Gram-negative bacteria appeared pink-red.

Controls for Gram Stain

- **Gram-Positive Control:** Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 25923
- **Gram-Negative Control:** Escherichia coli ATCC 25922

Culture and Identification: Samples were inoculated on 5% sheep blood agar and MacConkey's agar plates, incubated aerobically at 37°C overnight. Bacterial growth was identified by colony morphology, Gram staining, motility, and relevant biochemical tests according to standard laboratory methods.

Biochemical Tests for Enterobacteriaceae

1. Cytochrome Oxidase Test

- **Principle:** Tests for cytochrome oxidase activity, indicating aerobic respiration.
- **Procedure:** Smear suspected colony on a commercial reagent disc.
- **Interpretation:** Deep blue color indicates positive.
- **Controls:**
 - Positive: Pseudomonas aeruginosa
 - Negative: Escherichia coli

2. Catalase Test

- **Principle:** Detects the breakdown of hydrogen peroxide into oxygen and water.
- **Procedure:** Immerse colony in 3% hydrogen peroxide solution on a glass slide.

- **Interpretation:** Copious bubbles indicate positive.
- **Controls:**
 - Positive: *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923
 - Negative: *Streptococcus pyogenes* ATCC 19615

3. Indole Test

- **Principle:** Tests for the production of indole from tryptophan.
- **Procedure:** Inoculate peptone water with the test organism, incubate, and add Kovac's reagent.
- **Interpretation:** Red surface layer indicates positive.
- **Controls:**
 - Positive: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922
 - Negative: *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC 13883

4. Detection of Motility

- **Procedure:** Hanging drop preparation using a cavity slide and bacterial suspension.
- **Interpretation:** Observing movement under a microscope indicates motility.

5. Methyl Red Test

- **Principle:** Detects acid production from glucose fermentation.
- **Procedure:** Inoculate MR/VP broth, incubate, and add methyl red indicator.
- **Interpretation:** Stable red color indicates positive.
- **Controls:**
 - Positive: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922
 - Negative: *Enterobacter aerogenes* ATCC 13048

6. Voges-Proskauer Test

- **Principle:** Detects acetyl methyl carbinol production from glucose fermentation.
- **Procedure:** Inoculate glucose phosphate broth, add Barritt's reagents, and observe.
- **Interpretation:** Red color indicates positive.
- **Controls:**
 - Positive: *Enterobacter aerogenes* ATCC 13048
 - Negative: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922

7. Citrate Utilization Test

- **Principle:** Detects the use of citrate as a carbon source.
- **Procedure:** Inoculate citrate agar slant and incubate.
- **Interpretation:** Deep blue color or growth indicates positive.
- **Controls:**

- Positive: *Enterobacter aerogenes* ATCC 13048
- Negative: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922

8. Urease Test

- **Principle:** Detects urease enzyme production.
- **Procedure:** Inoculate Christensen urease agar and incubate.
- **Interpretation:** Red color indicates positive.
- **Controls:**
 - Positive: *Proteus* species
 - Negative: *Escherichia coli*

9. Triple Sugar Iron Agar Test

- **Principle:** Detects fermentation of glucose, lactose, sucrose, and H₂S production.
- **Procedure:** Inoculate TSI agar and incubate.
- **Interpretation:** Yellow color and black precipitate indicate positive.
- **Controls:**
 - A/A with gas: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922
 - K/A with H₂S: *Proteus mirabilis* ATCC 12453
 - K/NC or K/K: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853

10. Coagulase Test

- **Principle:** Detects free and bound coagulase in *Staphylococcus aureus*.
- **Procedure:** Perform slide and tube coagulase tests.
- **Interpretation:** Clumping or clot formation indicates positive.
- **Controls:**
 - Positive: *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923
 - Negative: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922

11. Oxidation-Fermentation (O-F) Test

- **Principle:** Differentiates oxidative from fermentative carbohydrate utilization.
- **Procedure:** Inoculate OF medium in open and sealed tubes.
- **Interpretation:** Yellow color in open tube indicates oxidative; in both tubes indicates fermentative.
- **Controls:**
 - Oxidative: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853
 - Fermentative: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922

Identification of Specific Bacteria

1. *Escherichia coli*

- **Morphology:** Gram-negative, motile bacilli.
 - **Cultural Characteristics:** Large colonies, hemolysis on blood agar, bright pink on MacConkey agar.
 - **Biochemical Characteristics:** Indole, Methyl Red positive; Voges Proskauer, Citrate, and Urease negative; acid production on TSI.
2. **Klebsiella pneumoniae**
- **Morphology:** Gram-negative, non-motile, capsulated bacilli.
 - **Cultural Characteristics:** Mucoid colonies on blood and MacConkey agar.
 - **Biochemical Characteristics:** Indole, Methyl Red negative; Voges Proskauer, Citrate, Urease positive; acid/acid with gas on TSI.
3. **Pseudomonas aeruginosa**
- **Morphology:** Slender, gram-negative bacillus.
 - **Cultural Characteristics:** Hemolytic colonies with fruity odor, non-lactose fermenting on MacConkey agar.
 - **Biochemical Characteristics:** Catalase, oxidase positive; K/K or no change in TSI.
4. **Acinetobacter species**
- **Morphology:** Gram-negative coccobacilli.
 - **Cultural Characteristics:** Non-hemolytic, pink colonies on MacConkey agar.
 - **Biochemical Characteristics:** Oxidase negative, K/K reaction in TSI, catalase positive, indole negative, citrate positive, urease negative.
5. **Staphylococcus aureus**
- **Morphology:** Gram-positive cocci in clusters.
 - **Cultural Characteristics:** Golden-yellow, hemolytic colonies on blood agar.
 - **Biochemical Characteristics:** Catalase, Coagulase positive.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing: Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar, following the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines. The antibiotics tested included ampicillin, ceftriaxone, erythromycin, clindamycin, linezolid, tetracycline, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, cefoxitin, gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, amoxicillin/clavulanic acid, piperacillin/tazobactam, cefuroxime, cefepime, imipenem, meropenem, amikacin, ceftazidime, ceftazidime/clavulanic acid, cefotaxime, and cefotaxime/clavulanic acid.

Procedure for Preparation of 0.5 McFarland Standard

1. Prepare 1% sulfuric acid and 1% barium chloride solutions.
2. Mix 0.6 ml of 1% barium chloride solution with 99.4 ml of 1% sulfuric acid solution, mix-

ing thoroughly to achieve a 0.5 McFarland standard.

3. The standard was stored in a dark place at room temperature in a tightly sealed tube.

Preparation of Inoculum

- A colony of the test organism was picked using a sterile loop and emulsified in 4-5 ml of sterile normal saline.
- The turbidity of the bacterial suspension was adjusted to match the 0.5 McFarland standards by adding more colonies or saline as necessary, comparing the tube against a card with white and black lines until the densities matched.

AST Procedure

1. A sterile cotton swab was dipped into the adjusted inoculum, with excess fluid removed by pressing and rotating the swab against the inner wall of the tube above the fluid level.
2. The entire agar surface of the Mueller-Hinton agar plate was swabbed evenly in three directions to ensure uniform inoculation.
3. The plate was allowed to dry for 3-5 minutes.
4. Antibiotic discs were placed on the agar surface using sterile forceps.
5. The plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 16-18 hours.
6. After incubation, the plates were examined and the diameters of the zones of inhibition were measured in millimeters using a ruler, with results interpreted according to CLSI guidelines.

Controls for AST

- **Positive Control:** Escherichia coli ATCC 25922
- **Negative Control:** Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 25923

Statistical Analysis:

Data collected were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS software version 20. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were used to summarize the data. The chi-square test was employed to determine the association between different variables, with a p-value of <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

Sample Collection and Culture Results: A total of 120 endotracheal secretion samples were collected and analyzed. Bacterial growth was observed in 86 samples (71.67%), while 34 samples (28.33%) showed no growth. Among the positive samples, 34 (28.33%) exhibited polymicrobial growth, and 52 (43.33%) exhibited monomicrobial growth.

Distribution of Isolates by Age and Gender

Age Distribution: The age distribution of patients from whom isolates were obtained is presented in Table 1. The majority of isolates were from pa-

tients aged 46-60 years (37.50%), followed by those above 60 years (22.50%).

The least number of isolates were from patients aged 0-15 years (5.83%).

Table 1: Distribution of Isolates by Age Group

Age Group (Years)	Total Isolates (n=120)	Percentage
0-15	7	5.83%
16-30	16	13.33%
31-45	25	20.83%
46-60	45	37.50%
Above 60	27	22.50%

Gender Distribution: Isolates were predominantly obtained from male patients (67.50%), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Isolates by Gender

Gender	Number of Isolates	Percentage
Male	81	67.50%
Female	39	32.50%

Distribution of Isolates by Organism: The most frequently isolated organisms were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (35.83%), followed by *Acinetobacter baumannii* (24.16%) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (23.33%), as detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of Isolates by Organism

Isolate	Number	Percentage
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	29	24.16%
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	28	23.33%
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	43	35.83%
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	11	9.16%
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	8	6.66%
<i>Streptococcus species</i>	1	0.83%

Antibiotic Sensitivity Patterns: The antibiotic sensitivity patterns of the isolates were analyzed. The data showed high resistance rates to common antibiotics among the isolates.

Sensitivity of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella*

***pneumoniae*:** *Escherichia coli* isolates were most sensitive to gentamicin (63.63%) and carbapenems (54.54%). In contrast, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* showed significant resistance, with only 45.45% sensitivity to imipenem and meropenem, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Sensitivity of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* to Antibiotics

Antibiotic	<i>E. coli</i> (n=11)	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (n=43)
	S	R
Trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole	3 (27.27%)	8 (72.72%)
Gentamicin	7 (63.63%)	4 (36.36%)
Piperacillin-tazobactam	5 (45.45%)	6 (54.54%)
Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid	3 (27.27%)	8 (72.72%)
Cefuroxime	1 (9.09%)	10 (90.90%)
Ciprofloxacin	3 (27.27%)	8 (72.72%)
Imipenem	6 (54.54%)	5 (45.45%)
Meropenem	6 (54.54%)	5 (45.45%)

Sensitivity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter baumannii*: Both *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter baumannii* exhibited high resistance to most tested antibiotics. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed the highest sensitivity to gentamicin (60.71%), while *Acinetobacter baumannii* exhibited significant resistance across all tested antibiotics, with sensitivity percentages below 40%, as detailed in Table 5.

Table 5: Sensitivity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter baumannii* to Antibiotics

Antibiotic	P. aeruginosa (n=28)	A. baumannii (n=29)
	S	R
Ceftazidime	8 (28.57%)	20 (71.42%)
Gentamicin	17 (60.71%)	11 (39.28%)
Piperacillin-tazobactam	8 (28.57%)	20 (71.42%)
Ciprofloxacin	10 (35.71%)	18 (64.28%)
Imipenem	10 (35.71%)	18 (64.28%)
Meropenem	11 (39.28%)	17 (60.71%)

Extended Spectrum β -Lactamases (ESBL) and Methicillin Resistance

ESBL-Producing Isolates: The prevalence of ESBL-producing isolates was notable, particularly among *Escherichia coli* (54.54%) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (18.60%), as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Distribution of ESBL-Producing Isolates

Organism	Total Isolates	ESBL Producer (%)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	43	8 (18.60%)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	11	6 (54.54%)

Sensitivity of ESBL-Producing Isolates: The ESBL-producing isolates exhibited high resistance to cephalosporins and limited sensitivity to carbapenems and aminoglycosides, as illustrated in Table 7.

Table 7: Antibiotic Sensitivity of ESBL-Producing Isolates

Antibiotic	E. coli (n=6)	K. pneumoniae (n=8)
	S	R
Trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole	2 (33.33%)	4 (66.66%)
Gentamicin	5 (83.33%)	1 (16.66%)
Piperacillin-tazobactam	4 (66.66%)	2 (33.33%)
Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid	2 (33.33%)	4 (66.66%)
Cefuroxime	0 (0%)	6 (100%)
Ciprofloxacin	2 (33.33%)	4 (66.66%)
Imipenem	5 (83.33%)	1 (16.66%)
Meropenem	5 (83.33%)	1 (16.66%)

Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA): Among the *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates, 87.50% were identified as MRSA, indicating a high prevalence of methicillin resistance, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Distribution of Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA)

Total Isolates	MRSA (%)
8	7 (87.50%)

The results reveal a significant prevalence of multi-drug-resistant organisms, particularly *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, in endotracheal secretions. The high resistance rates, especially among ESBL-producing strains and MRSA, underscore the need for vigilant antimicrobial stewardship and individualized treatment strategies to combat these infections effectively. Continuous monitoring and tailored antibiotic therapies are crucial in managing infections in critical care settings.

Discussion

This study aimed to characterize bacterial isolates and their antibiotic resistance patterns in endotracheal secretions from mechanically ventilated patients in intensive care units (ICUs). The findings offer significant insights into the prevalent pathogens and their resistance profiles, providing a foundation for improving empirical antibiotic therapy

and infection management in this vulnerable patient population [9].

Prevalence and Distribution of Bacterial Isolates: In this study, 120 endotracheal secretion samples were analyzed, with 86 samples showing bacterial growth. The most frequently isolated organisms were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (35.83%), *Acinetobacter baumannii* (24.16%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (23.33%) [10]. These findings are consistent with previous research highlighting the prominence of these pathogens in ICU-acquired infections. *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, in particular, has been identified as a leading cause of nosocomial infections in ventilated patients due to its ability to form biofilms and its resistance to multiple antibiotics [11].

The high prevalence of *Acinetobacter baumannii* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is also noteworthy. Both are known for their environmental persistence and high resistance potential, making them chal-

lenging to manage in clinical settings. The predominance of these pathogens underscores the necessity for vigilant infection control practices and targeted antibiotic stewardship [12].

Antibiotic Resistance Patterns: The antibiotic susceptibility profiles revealed significant resistance among the isolates. For *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, resistance to commonly used antibiotics such as cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin, and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid was observed. The high resistance rates in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* are particularly concerning, as this organism is known for producing extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs), which confer resistance to a broad range of β -lactam antibiotics [13]. The detection of ESBL-producing strains of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in 18.60% of cases highlights the need for rapid diagnostic testing and the use of alternative treatment options for these infections.

Similarly, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter baumannii* exhibited considerable resistance to antibiotics such as ceftazidime, gentamicin, and carbapenems. The resistance profiles of these pathogens are consistent with global trends, where multi-drug-resistant strains pose significant treatment challenges [14]. The observed resistance to imipenem and meropenem in a substantial proportion of *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates reflects the increasing prevalence of carbapenem-resistant strains.

Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA): The study found that 87.50% of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates were methicillin-resistant. This high prevalence of MRSA is consistent with reports from other studies, indicating that MRSA remains a major concern in ICU settings [15]. The resistance to methicillin and other antibiotics emphasizes the need for rigorous infection control measures and the potential utility of alternative treatment options such as linezolid or vancomycin in managing MRSA infections.

Clinical Implications: The high levels of antibiotic resistance observed in this study highlight the urgent need for tailored antibiotic therapies based on local resistance patterns. The data suggest that empirical treatment regimens should be carefully selected to account for the high prevalence of resistant organisms, particularly in patients with prolonged ICU stays or those who have received prior antibiotic treatment [16]. Regular surveillance of antibiotic resistance patterns and the implementation of stewardship programs are critical to combat the spread of resistant pathogens.

Furthermore, the presence of polymicrobial infections in 28.33% of the samples underscores the complexity of managing infections in critically ill patients. This highlights the importance of comprehensive diagnostic approaches, including the use of

broad-spectrum antibiotics and subsequent de-escalation based on susceptibility testing [17].

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of bacterial isolates and their antibiotic resistance patterns in endotracheal secretions from mechanically ventilated ICU patients. Our findings highlight the following key points:

1. **Prevalent Pathogens:** The most frequently isolated bacteria were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (35.83%), *Acinetobacter baumannii* (24.16%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (23.33%). These pathogens are known for their significant role in ICU-acquired infections and their potential to cause severe complications [18].
2. **Antibiotic Resistance:** There was a high prevalence of antibiotic resistance among the isolates. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli* exhibited substantial resistance to commonly used antibiotics, including cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin, and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid [19]. Notably, 18.60% of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates were ESBL producers, underscoring the need for alternative treatment options and rapid diagnostic methods.
3. **Resistance in *Pseudomonas* and *Acinetobacter*:** Both *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter baumannii* showed considerable resistance to critical antibiotics such as ceftazidime, gentamicin, and carbapenems. This resistance highlights the challenges in managing infections caused by these organisms and the necessity for ongoing surveillance and targeted therapies [20].
4. **High MRSA Prevalence:** A significant proportion of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates (87.50%) were methicillin-resistant, reflecting the continued challenge posed by MRSA in ICU settings.

The results of this study emphasize the critical need for tailored antibiotic therapies based on local resistance patterns and the importance of stringent infection control measures. The high levels of resistance observed necessitate the implementation of effective antimicrobial stewardship programs to guide treatment decisions and curb the spread of resistant pathogens.

Overall, the data underscores the importance of continuous monitoring and adaptation of treatment protocols to address the evolving landscape of antibiotic resistance, thereby improving patient outcomes in intensive care settings.

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